

Evaluating the consistency of ANA results: A cross-method study of three immunodiagnostic techniques*

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Abstract

Objectives: Indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) on HEp-2 cells is the gold standard for antinuclear antibody (ANA) screening, followed by antigen-specific confirmation using immunoassays such as immunoblot (IB) and ELISA. This study aimed to compare antigen-specific ANA/ENA results obtained by these three methods.

Materials and methods: Serum samples from 100 individuals (mean age 47 years; 12 men, 88 women) were analyzed. ANA screening was performed by IIF on HEp-2 cells (ANA-HEp-2, ByoSystems) using a EUROStar III Plus fluorescence microscope; titers >1:80 were considered positive. IB was performed using ANA Profile 3 plus DFS70 (EUROIMMUN). ELISA testing included SS-A, SS-B, Scl-70, and dsDNA-NcX (EUROIMMUN), and RNP/Sm, Jo-1, and AMA-M2 (Orgentec).

Results: Based on IIF, participants were classified as ANA-positive (n = 48), borderline (n = 26), or ANA-negative (n = 26). The most frequent IB reactivities were SS-A, Ro-52, centromere B, and AMA-M2. In ANA-negative and borderline groups, IB signal intensity >20 was detected for SS-A (n = 2), Ro-52 (n = 4), and Scl-70 (n = 3). Among ANA-positive individuals, ICAP pattern interpretation showed concordance with IB in 40 cases and discordance in two cases. Agreement between ELISA and IB varied by antigen (50%–88%), with the highest concordance for SS-A. Correlation between IB and ELISA ranged from moderate to very strong (r = 0.5–>0.9).

Conclusion: IIF, IB, and ELISA provide complementary information, with variable sensitivities and clinically relevant agreement, underscoring the need for a structured diagnostic algorithm combined with clinical context.

Keywords

ANA, antinuclear antibodies, ELISA, IIF, immunoblot

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Introduction

Antinuclear antibodies (ANAs) are a class of autoantibodies that target various antigens within the cell nucleus and are typically associated with autoimmune disorders, often related to chronic inflammation and tissue damage (Nosal et al. 2025). The presence of ANA is most commonly linked to systemic autoimmune diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), rheumatoid arthritis (RA) (Zagorov et al. 2006), Sjögren's disease, polymyositis, and dermatomyositis (Castro and Gourley 2010), as well as some organ-specific diseases such as autoimmune hepatitis and primary biliary cirrhosis. However, a positive ANA test result is not exclusive to autoimmune conditions – ANA production has also been observed in the context of chronic infections, including tuberculosis, histoplasmosis, and Epstein–Barr virus (mononucleosis) (Zagorov et al. 2005; Im et al. 2020); administration of certain medications (e.g., antihypertensives, antibiotics, antifungals, and chemotherapeutics) (Dinse et al. 2018); solid organ cancers (including lung, breast, and colon cancers) (Vlagea et al. 2018); and radiation therapy. Additionally, ANA positivity may occur in otherwise healthy individuals, particularly with increasing age, likely due to cumulative environmental exposures (e.g., infections, medications, and pollutants) that affect immune tolerance (Grygiel-Górniak et al. 2018).

Given the broad differential for ANA positivity, accurate and standardized diagnostic testing is critical. The three primary methods for ANA detection include indirect immunofluorescence (IIF), enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), and immunoblot (IB), each offering distinct advantages and limitations in clinical practice. IIF on HEp-2 cells remains the gold standard for ANA screening (Damoiseaux et al. 2019). This method involves incubating serial dilutions of a patient's serum on substrate sections, followed by the application of fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-conjugated anti-IgG antibodies for detection. The resulting fluorescence patterns, classified according to the International Consensus on ANA Patterns (ICAP), are associated with specific autoantibodies and clinical conditions (Chan et al. 2022). Moreover, ICAP provides a unified system that seeks to standardize ANA test interpretation, harmonize autoantibody nomenclature, and promote accurate recognition of morphological patterns in clinical diagnostics (Andrade et al. 2024).

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is designed to detect specific ANA targets by immobilizing antigens on a solid surface and employing enzyme-linked antibodies to generate a measurable signal (Kumar et al. 2025). Due to its high sensitivity and ease of use, ELISA is widely adopted in both clinical and research settings. It is especially useful for quantifying antibody concentrations and efficiently screening large patient populations. Similarly, IB, also referred to as Western blot, employs gel electrophoresis to separate proteins, which are then transferred to a membrane and probed with specific antibodies. This technique is well suited for confirming the presence of antibodies against distinct nuclear antigens. IB yields both qualitative and semi-quantitative data, contributing

to the identification of disease-specific autoantibody profiles and biomarkers (Öztürk et al. 2022).

In addition to IIF on HEp-2 cells, several solid-phase immunoassay platforms are currently available for antigen-specific ANA/ENA detection, including chemiluminescent immunoassays (CLIA), fluoroenzyme immunoassays (FEIA), and addressable laser bead immunoassays (ALBIA). These technologies may offer advantages such as automation, high throughput, and standardized read-out; however, their performance depends on the selected antigen panels and assay design. In routine clinical practice, the choice of method is often influenced by laboratory availability, cost, and diagnostic workflow. Multiplex bead-based immunoassays (e.g., Luminex) represent an additional ANA testing approach with high throughput; however, their implementation may be limited by cost and availability in routine outpatient laboratories.

Our study aims to analyze and compare diagnostic results from IIF, ELISA, and IB when applied concurrently to a shared patient cohort. Additionally, it aims to assess the degree of concordance and the nature of discrepancies among these three immunological methods in detecting antinuclear antibodies.

Materials and methods

Materials

This study included 100 serum samples obtained from patients (12 men and 88 women) with a mean age of 47 years. All samples were analyzed using three immunological methods for the detection of antinuclear antibodies: IIF, ELISA, and IB.

Immunological methods

ANA screening was performed using HEp-2 cell substrates (ByoSystems). Samples were considered positive if fluorescence was observed at a titer greater than 1:80. Testing was conducted according to standard immunofluorescence protocols for ANA detection. To ensure standardized interpretation and reporting of HEp-2 IIF results, fluorescence patterns were classified according to the International Consensus on ANA Patterns (ICAP). ICAP provides a harmonized nomenclature for HEp-2 IIF patterns using alphanumeric “AC” codes (AntiCell patterns), facilitating reproducibility across laboratories and improving communication between clinicians and diagnostic services. Each AC pattern reflects a characteristic cellular staining distribution (e.g., nuclear, cytoplasmic, or mitotic) and may suggest the presence of specific autoantibody reactivities. However, antigen-level confirmation requires additional solid-phase assays. In this study, ICAP-based pattern classification was used to support consistent reporting of IIF findings and to enable comparison with antigen-specific results obtained by immunoblot and ELISA.

The ELISA method was employed to detect antibodies against seven nuclear antigens. Antibodies against SS-A,

SS-B, Scl-70, and dsDNA-NcX were measured using kits provided by EUROIMMUN, while antibodies against RNP/Sm, Jo-1, and AMA-M2 were detected using kits from Orgentec (Alegria, Germany).

Immunoblotting was conducted using the EURO-LINE ANA Profile 3 plus DFS70 kit (cat. no. DL 1590-6401-30G, EUROIMMUN), which detects IgG antibodies against 16 nuclear and cytoplasmic antigens: RNP/Sm, Sm, SS-A, Ro-52, SS-B, Scl-70, PM-Scl100, Centromere B, PCNA, dsDNA, nucleosomes, histones, ribosomal protein, AMA-M2, and DFS70. All procedures were carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions. Sample processing and analysis were performed using the EURO-BlotOne automated blotter (44 slots) and EuroLineScan software (EUROIMMUN, Germany). Signals with intensity above 11 were considered positive, while those above six were considered borderline.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 28.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were used. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables, while means and standard deviations were used for continuous variables. Concordance (agreement) between the different ANA detection methods (IIF, ELISA, and immunoblot) was assessed using the Pearson coefficient, with values interpreted as follows: <0.20 poor agreement, 0.21–0.40 fair, 0.41–0.60 moderate, 0.61–0.80 good, and >0.80 very good agreement. Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to evaluate the linear relationship between quantitative results obtained from ELISA and immunoblot assays for specific antigen targets. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ for all analyses.

Results

Grouping based on ANA titers and specific antibodies assessed by IB

The study population was categorized into three groups based on IIF screening results using HEp-2 cells. Group 1 (ANA-positive) included 48 individuals with ANA titers greater than 1:80. Group 2 (ANA-negative) comprised 26 individuals with titers below 1:80, and Group 3 (borderline ANA) consisted of 26 individuals with an ANA titer equal to 1:80.

In Group 1 (ANA-positive; $n = 48$), the most frequently detected autoantigens by immunoblot were SS-A (16/48), Ro-52 (15/48), Centromere B (CB; 11/48), and AMA-M2 (9/48). These findings highlight the predominance of specific extractable nuclear antigens in individuals with ANA-positive status. In contrast, among Group 2 (ANA-negative; $n = 26$) and Group 3 (ANA-borderline; $n = 26$), relevant antigen expression was still observed, although at lower frequencies.

Notably, SS-A was detected in three and two patients from Groups 2 and 3, respectively; Ro-52 in two and two;

AMA-M2 in three and one; Scl-70 in one and three; and PM-Scl-100 in four and one patients, respectively. Additionally, the autoantibody DFS70 was detected in 14% of participants, regardless of the ANA titer group, suggesting its broader distribution across ANA profiles. These findings highlight the variability in antigen expression and the potential clinical relevance of immunoblot testing, even in patients with negative or borderline ANA results from IIF.

Agreement between IB and IIF

The highest concordance was observed in the ANA-positive group, whereas the borderline and negative titer groups showed greater discordance and a higher proportion of unmatched antigens (Fig. 1). The agreement between indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) and immunoblot (IB) results was evaluated by stratifying the cohort by ANA titer into three groups: ANA-negative (<1:80), borderline (=1:80), and ANA-positive (>1:80) (Fig. 1). In the ANA-positive group, IIF and IB showed high concordance, indicating that antigen-specific reactivity detected by IB generally corresponded to ICAP-based fluorescence findings. In contrast, lower concordance and higher discordance were observed in the ANA-negative and border-

Figure 1. Comparison between immunoblot (IB) and indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) results stratified by ANA titer. Patients were classified into three groups according to IIF titer: ANA-negative (<1:80), borderline (=1:80), and ANA-positive (>1:80). Concordance (%) indicates the proportion of cases in which the IB result agreed with the IIF-based ANA classification within each group. Discordance (%) indicates disagreement between IIF classification and IB results (e.g., IIF-negative or borderline with IB positivity, or IIF-positive with no corresponding IB reactivity). Antigenes not present on the blot (%) refers to cases in which IIF showed fluorescence suggestive of autoantibody reactivity against targets not included in the IB assay antigen panel, preventing direct antigen-level comparison. Fluorescence of other antigenes (%) indicates IIF fluorescence patterns directed to cellular structures not represented in the IB assay and therefore not captured by IB antigen detection.

line groups, reflecting cases with weak or borderline fluorescence intensity and low-level antigen reactivity.

Importantly, a subset of samples showed fluorescence patterns suggestive of reactivity against targets that are not included in the IB antigen panel (“antigens not present on the blot”), which limits direct antigen-level matching between IIF and IB. Additionally, “fluorescence of other antigens” refers to cases in which IIF detected staining of cellular structures that are not represented in the immunoblot assay and therefore cannot be confirmed by IB. Overall, these findings highlight that IIF and IB provide complementary information and that discrepancies may arise from differences in antigen coverage and analytical sensitivity (Fig. 1).

Agreement between IB and ELISA results

The degree of concordance between IB and ELISA varied by antigen and ANA group. Pearson correlation coefficients were interpreted according to standard thresholds: 0–0.3 indicating weak correlation, 0.3–0.5 moderate, 0.5–0.7 significant, 0.7–0.9 strong, and >0.9 very strong agreement (Table 1).

Table 1. Pearson correlation coefficients between ELISA and immunoblot (IB) results for specific antigens in ANA testing.

ELISA	IIB	Pearson coeff.	P value
DsDNA-NcX	Nucleosomes b	0.638	0.000021
DsDNA-NcX	dsDNA	0.170	0.315
DsDNA-NcX	Histones	0.263	0.116
DsDNA-NcX	Ribosomal protein	0.333	0.0439
RNP/Sm	RNP/Sm	0.900	0.000027
SS-A	SS-A	0.864	<0.000001
SS-B	SS-B	0.777	<0.000001
Scl-70	Scl-70	0.992	<0.000001
AMA-M2	AMA-M2	0.707	0.00103
Jo-1	Jo-1	0.615	0.0783

Strongest correlations were observed for Scl-70 (ELISA vs. IB), RNP/Sm (ELISA vs. IB), and SS-A (ELISA vs. IB) (Fig. 2A). At the same time, weaker associations were found for dsDNA (ELISA vs. IB), and moderate associations were found for dsDNA-NcX (ELISA) versus nucleosomes (IB) (Fig. 2B).

Agreement between IB and ELISA

In the ANA-positive group (Group 1), concordance between IB and ELISA ranged from 50% to 83%, with the highest level of agreement observed for SS-A and nucleosomes. These findings suggest that these antigens are robustly detected across both platforms in patients with high ANA titers. In Groups 2 and 3 (ANA-negative and borderline ANA), agreement was limited but notable. Two individuals exhibited matching results for the Jo-1 antigen, and three individuals demonstrated concordance for SS-A, Scl-70, and AMA-M2 (Table 2). Despite lower ANA titers or negative IIF screening, IB and ELISA identified overlapping antigen profiles in select cases, supporting their complementary diagnostic value.

In Group 1, the correlation between IB and ELISA results varied depending on the specific autoantibody being tested. A very strong correlation ($r > 0.9$) was observed between RNP/Sm and Scl-70, indicating high agreement between the two methods for these targets. Strong correlations ($r = 0.7–0.9$) were found for RNP/Sm ($r = 0.819$), SS-A ($r = 0.682$), and SS-B ($r = 0.707$), further supporting the diagnostic reliability of parallel testing. In contrast, moderate correlations ($r = 0.5–0.7$) were observed for nucleosomes (NUC), Jo-1 ($r = 0.615$), and AMA-M2 ($r = 0.665$), suggesting greater variability across assays for these antigens.

Agreement between IIF and IB results in patients with ANA titer >1:80

The ANA-positive group (Group 1: ANA titer >1:80) consisted of 48 individuals (5 men and 43 women) with a mean age of 46 years. A high degree of concordance was observed between IIF and IB, with 40 of 48 cases showing matched results. In two cases, no match was detected between the IIF and IB findings (Fig. 3). Additionally, four patients showed positive immunofluorescence staining for antigens not represented in the immunoblot panel, indicating possible reactivity to other nuclear or cytoplasmic targets. Notably, two individuals exhibited no defined fluorescent pattern according to ICAP criteria despite having detectable anti-Ro52 antibodies, suggesting a limitation in pattern recognition for this specificity using IIF alone.

Figure 2. Correlation between ELISA and immunoblot (IB) results for selected antigens in ANA testing. **A.** Nucleosomes detected by IB versus dsDNA-NcX detected by ELISA, showing a moderate positive correlation; **B.** SS-A (60 kDa) detected by IB versus ELISA, showing a strong positive correlation. Red dotted lines represent positive linear regression fits.

Table 2. Frequency (%) of specific autoantibody detection by immunoblot in relation to ANA titer groups.

ANA titer	dsDNA-NcX									
	RNP/S	SS-A	SS-B	Scl-70	AMA-M2	Jo-1	Nucleosomes	dsDNA	Histones	Ribosomal protein
ANA > 1:80	72%	82%	50%	50%	67%	50%	83%	50%	33%	50%
ANA = 1:80	0	0	0	0	0	25%	0	0	0	0
ANA < 1:80	0	50%	0	33%	20%	33%	0	0	0	0

IIF vs immunoblot

Figure 3. Comparison of ANA detection results obtained by indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) and immunoblot (IB).

In this study, IIF on HEp-2 cells revealed a variety of ANA staining patterns, each associated with distinct autoantibody specificities and potential clinical correlations. The most frequent patterns included homogeneous (AC-1), centromere (AC-3), multiple nuclear dots (AC-6), cytoplasmic reticular (AC-21), and speckled nucleolar (AC-8). These patterns were associated with specific antibodies, including anti-dsDNA, anti-CENP, anti-Sp100, anti-AMA, and anti-PM-Scl, respectively, and are illustrated in Fig. 4. Recognition of these characteristic flu-

orescence patterns is essential for guiding subsequent confirmatory testing by IB or ELISA and for correlating results with clinical presentation.

Discussion

A wide variety of nuclear staining patterns – such as homogeneous, speckled, nucleolar, centromere, nuclear membrane, cytoplasmic, and mitotic – can be observed in ANA testing using IIF on HEp-2 cells. These patterns often correlate with specific autoantibodies that are more accurately characterized using antigen-specific assays, such as ELISA and immunoblot. Since the clinical relevance of ANA patterns stems from their association with specific autoimmune conditions, confirmatory testing is essential. However, certain autoantibodies – such as anti-Ro52 – may not be reliably detected by IIF alone due to limitations in substrate cell line expression or assay sensitivity. In such scenarios, the complementary use of ELISA or immunoblotting is advisable. On the other hand, it is important to note that not all fluorescence patterns visualized by IIF correspond to antigens included in standard ELISA or immunoblot panels. Therefore, a comprehensive diagnostic strategy often requires the integration of multiple testing modalities to ensure accurate identification of disease-specific autoantibodies, which informs our primary goal – to analyze and compare the diagnostic results obtained through IIF, ELISA, and IB when applied

Figure 4. Representative ANA patterns observed by indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) on HEp-2 cells: different nuclear and cytoplasmic staining patterns associated with specific autoantibodies. **AC-1** (homogeneous pattern) – anti-dsDNA, anti-ssDNA, anti-nucleosome, and anti-histone antibodies; **AC-3** (centromere pattern) – anti-CENP-A and -B antibodies; **AC-6** (multiple nuclear dots) – anti-Sp100, anti-Sp140, and anti-PML antibodies; **AC-6/AC-21** (cytoplasmic reticular pattern) – anti-AMA antibodies; **AC-8** (speckled nucleolar pattern) – anti-PM-Scl antibodies. These patterns correlate with specific autoimmune disease profiles, aiding in targeted serological testing.

concurrently to a shared patient cohort – and, secondarily, to assess the degree of concordance and the nature of discrepancies among these three immunological methods in detecting antinuclear antibodies.

The concordance rate between IIF and immunoblot observed in our ANA-positive group (83.3%) is consistent with prior research, which shows high agreement for commonly expressed antigens such as histones and nucleosomes (Robbins et al. 2019; Jang et al. 2021). However, discrepancies in detection – particularly for Ro-52 – have been frequently reported and are attributed to differences in substrate sensitivity or antigen representation across methods (Sarafian et al. 2004; Yang et al. 2023).

We found that the degree of concordance between IB and ELISA results varied across Group 1 (>1:80), depending on the specific autoantibody target. The highest agreement was observed for RNP/Sm and Scl-70, where very strong correlations ($r > 0.9$) indicated excellent consistency between the two methodologies for these antigens. Strong correlations were also demonstrated for RNP/Sm ($r = 0.819$), SS-A ($r = 0.682$), and SS-B ($r = 0.707$), reinforcing the diagnostic reliability of applying both techniques in parallel. In contrast, moderate correlations were noted for nucleosomes (NUC), Jo-1 ($r = 0.615$), and AMA-M2 ($r = 0.665$), suggesting greater inter-assay variability for these analytes. This variability may reflect differences in antigen presentation between platforms, analytical sensitivity, or epitope specificity and should be taken into account when interpreting results in a clinical context. Murdjeva et al. (2011) also reported very good agreement ($\kappa = 0.890$) between IFA-ANA and ELISA for ANA screening. Additionally, very good agreement was observed for the determination of specific antibodies by IB and ELISA, including anti-SS-A ($\kappa = 1.000$), SS-B ($\kappa = 1.000$), and anti-dsDNA ($\kappa = 0.825$); moderate agreement for anti-Sm and anti-Sm/RNP ($\kappa = 0.479$); and fair agreement for anti-histone/nucleosome ANA ($\kappa = 0.303$).

While IIF remains the gold standard for ANA screening due to its broad pattern recognition and high sensitivity, its interpretative subjectivity and dependence on operator expertise can lead to false-negative results (Carbone et al. 2018; Turan Faraşat et al. 2019). ELISA and immunoblot provide more objective, antigen-specific results but may fail to detect rare autoantibodies that are not included in commercial panels (Alsaed et al. 2021; Irure-Ventura and Marcos 2022).

Regarding subjectivity, Li et al. (2019) compared automated ANA recognition with conventional visual interpretation, demonstrating 98.7% agreement in 3,681 resting samples. However, the efficiency of automated recognition for a single pattern varied among different antigens. Our data support the complementary use of IIF and antigen-specific tests to increase diagnostic accuracy. This approach is particularly important in patients undergoing immunosuppressive therapy, in whom ANA titers may fluctuate or become indeterminate (Grygiel-Górniak et al. 2018; Kutlu et al. 2020; Kraev et al. 2024; Nakano et al. 2025).

Almost perfect inter-assay agreement for antibodies against Ro52/Ro60, CENP-B, and Scl-70 ($\kappa = 0.91$ – 1.00) was demonstrated for IIF vs. extractable nuclear antigens (ENAs) detected by ELISA, with additional strong agreement for anti-SS-B/La antibodies ($\kappa = 0.81$) and low agreement for antibodies against dsDNA, Sm, RNP, and Jo-1 (Jang et al. 2021).

According to our results, the strong correlation for RNP/Sm and Scl-70 in Group 1 may reflect the robustness of their antigenic epitopes across both IIF and IB detection platforms. Conversely, the moderate correlation observed for AMA-M2 may be due to epitope masking or assay interference.

Alsaed et al. (2021) investigated the performance of ANA assessed by ELISA (ANA detect) versus IIF for screening patients with connective tissue diseases (CTDs), analyzing a total of 12,439 ANA tests. Using a dilutional titer of $\geq 1:80$ as the ANA-IIF cutoff and 1.0 for ANA-ELISA, the sensitivity of ANA-IIF and ANA-ELISA for all CTDs was 63.3% and 74.8%, respectively; however, the overall specificity of ANA-ELISA was 89.05%, which was slightly higher than that of ANA-IIF (86.72%).

Similarly, González Rodríguez et al. (2021) confirmed that IIF screening demonstrated superior diagnostic accuracy (79% sensitivity, 91% specificity) compared with ELISA or IIF alone. When combined with IIF, sensitivity increased to 93%, representing the highest detection rate. ENA profiling identified Ro52 and Ro60 as the most frequently detected specificities. Notably, IIF alone failed to detect up to 36% of Ro52-positive and 41% of Ro60-positive samples. The authors concluded that combining ELISA and IB with IIF markedly enhances sensitivity and overall diagnostic accuracy for systemic autoimmune rheumatic diseases, findings that are consistent with our results.

Future directions

Future research should aim to expand immunoblot panels to include less common ANA targets and to evaluate assay performance across diverse patient cohorts.

Limitations and strengths of the study

This study is limited by its single-laboratory design and the potential influence of assay-specific variability. A multicenter comparison could further validate these findings. Nevertheless, the study offers valuable insights into diagnostic concordance and discrepancies among three widely used ANA detection methods – indirect immunofluorescence (IIF), ELISA, and immunoblot – by applying them simultaneously to a shared patient cohort. One key strength is the real-world design, reflecting routine diagnostic workflows in a high-throughput immunology laboratory. Additionally, the use of ICAP classification criteria for ANA pattern interpretation enhances the reproducibility and comparability of IIF results. The study also provides a detailed analysis of antigen-specific findings,

contributing to the optimization of diagnostic algorithms for autoimmune diseases.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size and single-center setting may limit the generalizability of the findings. Although methodological consistency was maintained, some patients did not undergo all three tests simultaneously, which may have introduced variability in the results. The subjective nature of IIF interpretation, despite ICAP guidance, and the limited antigen spectrum of commercial ELISA and immunoblot kits may affect the comprehensiveness of autoantibody detection. Because ELISA testing was performed only for a limited antigen panel (SS-A, SS-B, Scl-70, RNP/Sm, Jo-1, and dsDNA-NcX), comprehensive IIF-ELISA pattern-antigen comparisons were restricted, particularly for antibodies such as SS-A/Ro and SS-B that do not consistently produce distinct HEp-2 IIF patterns. Consequently, IIF and ELISA were not directly compared. Furthermore, the study did not include detailed clinical variables, such as disease activity, symptom duration, or treatment status other than biological therapy, which could have refined the interpretation of discordant results.

Conclusion

ANA detection is primarily performed using three methods: immunofluorescence and the immunoenzymatic methods ELISA and immunoblot, which differ in sensitivity and clinical significance. Each technique exhibits distinct sensitivity profiles and clinical applicability, underscoring their combined value in diagnosing autoimmune diseases, chronic infections, drug-induced autoimmunity, neoplastic processes, and other immunologically mediated conditions. We aimed to investigate the differences between methods by simultaneously testing patients using all three approaches and analyzing the complementary results to determine ANA titers and the spectrum of target antigens. The comparative analysis demonstrates that the immunological methods used for ANA detection offer complementary strengths, with high correlation and concordance across platforms. The selected immunological methods for ANA determination are supplementary, showing good correlation and agreement. To optimize diagnostic accuracy and clinical interpretation, we recommend implementing a structured diagnostic algorithm that integrates serological results with patient-specific clinical data.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, T.V. and A.M.; methodology, S.Z., P.D., P.S., M.K., B.A. and M.B.; software, P.D.; validation, P.S., A.M., S.Z. and T.V.; formal analysis, A.M. and T.V.; investigation, E.P., R.M. and B.P.; resources, R.M.; data curation, S.Z., P.D. and B.P.; writing—original draft preparation, T.V. and A.M.; writing—review and editing, P.S. and B.P.; visualization, A.M. and T.V.; supervision, T.V.; project administration, A.M. and B.P.; funding acquisition, T.V. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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